

BOARD STRUCTURE AND AGGRESSIVE TAX AVOIDANCE EMPIRICAL EVIDENCE FROM NIGERIA INSURANCE FIRMS.

**¹Jinadu Margaret. N. (Ph.D.), ²Ijemba, Onyinyechukwu N. (Ph.D.) and
³Ezema Clifford Anene (Ph.D.)**

¹Department of Insurance, Collage of Social and Management Sciences, Lagos State University of Science and Technology, (LASUSUTECH), Lagos State

²Coordinator, General Study Division, Collage of Nursing Sciences, University of Nigeria Teaching Hospital, Ituku Ozzala. Enugu State. Nigeria.

³Department of Insurance and Risk Management, Faculty of Management Sciences, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, (ESUT), Enugu, Research interest, Finance, Insurance and Risk management.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20646831>

ABSTRACT: *The study examined the effect of board structure and aggressive tax avoidance in Nigeria Insurance Industry. The specific objectives of the study were to: examine the effect of Corporate Board Size, Corporate Board Independence, Corporate Board Diversity on tax management in Nigeria Insurance Industry. The study used an ex post facto research design. Data were collected through secondary sources from the selected from Insurance companies in Nigeria which was analyzed using multiple panel regression analysis with the aid of E-view 10. The study revealed that Corporate Board Size had a significant effect on tax management in Nigeria Insurance Industry. (Where the t-value = -2.717285 and P-value = 0.0092), that Corporate Board Independence did not significantly effect on tax management in Nigeria Insurance Industry. (Where the t-value = 0.184291 and P-value = 0.8546), and that Corporate Board Diversity had no significant effect on tax management in Nigeria Insurance Industry. (Where t-value of 1.039607 and P-value of 0.3040). The study concluded that corporate governance has not influenced tax on tax management in Nigeria Insurance Industry. This is because corporate tax aggressiveness is considered as one of the most severe compliance issues threatening Nigeria and most nations of the world. The study recommended that insurance industry should maintain a moderate board size, due to the need to facilitate quality and timely decision-making, board efficacy, and compliance with tax law provisions and authority; Also management should examine their tax aggressive activities of the government to ensure that it does not affect the performance of the firm negatively so as to give value to diversity in the board composition within the firm as diversity in the board decreases tax aggressiveness.*

KEYWORDS: *Tax Avoidance, Insurance firms, Board Independence. Board Size.*

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The importance of corporate governance mechanisms through board structure in influencing every aspect of corporate management including tax expense reduction cannot be over emphasized. It is the heart of every company and takes a center stage in its affairs. The financial performance of firms and realization of shareholder's wealth depends majorly on the quality of corporate governance mechanisms. Effective corporate governance mechanisms are necessary factors to promote efficient management of the affairs of a firm and realization of its set goals and objectives (Aliani & Zarai, 2012). Efficient management implies reduction of costs of operations like administrative expenses, expansion of the business product lines and customer base as well as the accommodating of tax laws. In doing this, cautions become vital so as to avoid tax evasion with a view to minimize taxable expenses which have the tendency to increase net income of the firm. Tax expenses usually are part of operating cost to a company and its shareholders. The board of director as a corporate governance mechanism is critical in decelerating tax expenses. Zemzem and Fluohi (2013), opine that corporate governance mechanism is interrelated with each other such as board size, managerial ownership, board independence, ownership concentration, board diversity, audit committee size, amongst others. (Ideh, & Okolo, 2025). In firms, the board of directors irrespective of the size has the duty to minimize expenses regarding tax and it is always responsible to the resource's owners and other stakeholders. The boards of directors and management employ every known and available strategy to minimize tax expenses in a legal way. What they do is ascertain the kind of tax expenses that are favorable if they minimize it within tax laws and take advantage of them to avoid excess tax payment for a period with the intention to increase net earnings. The reduction of tax expense is commonly referred to as tax aggressiveness (Aliani & Zarai, 2012). Ultimately tax aggressiveness is presumed to increase net income and influences shareholders' wealth maximization (Konstantinos, 2016).

Abrahman (2011) posits that corporate governance mechanism is a significant factor that influences tax aggressiveness. The use of corporate governance mechanisms to minimize tax payments no doubt is borne out of tax management proficiency, managerial ingenuity, expertise and sincerity of purpose geared towards the achievement of shareholders' wealth in an organization while being cautious of sliding into the trap of tax evasion. Through aggressive tax practices/behaviour by management, revenue accruable to the government from taxation is reduced. Tax aggressive activities are very germane to achieve optimal firm financial performance, all things being equal. Tax aggressiveness is often carried out through effective strategies. These strategies become effective if they enable firms to reduce tax cost and increase earnings. Strategies employed to carry out tax aggressiveness by quoted firms are in form of allowable items which are deductible according to tax laws. They are deductions permitted in tax laws which managers can take advantage of to reduce tax cost. The lower the cost of tax expense, the higher the investment returns, expressed as profit for a period. Tax aggressiveness has its adverse implications. One of the adverse implications of tax aggressiveness is tax invasion. It does

not only affect the image of the company, but it may affect shareholders' investment resources. The favorable economic implication of tax aggressiveness is decreasing of tax costs. (Shaba, & Idris, 2024). Many of the studies on corporate governance mechanism and tax aggressiveness of listed companies have produced divergent results. The empirical results of prior researches remained inconclusive. In Nigeria for instance, there are little empirics as regards the influence of corporate governance mechanism like board size, managerial ownership, board gender diversity, ownership concentration and board independence on tax aggressiveness of listed firms in the insurance industry on evidence.

2.0 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATUR

Conceptual Review

Corporate Governance Using board structure

Corporate Governance deals with the way the investors make sure they get a fair return on their investment. In Corporate Governance, there is a clear distinction between the role of the owners of a company (the shareholders) and the managers (the executive board of directors) when it comes to making effective strategic decisions which tax planning could be one of those decisions. Okafor (2009) posits that the main idea behind corporate governance is to direct and control the activities of corporate entities in order for interested parties have returns on their investment from the companies. Corporate governance plays a fundamental role in monitoring different actors and harnessing on planning procedures in an organization. Corporate governance has a global vision of the activities of management, but the question of its performance had been several debates and disputes in time and in space, as a way to rehabilitate the informational efficiency (Boussaidi & Hamed, 2015). Corporate governance arises due to principal-agent problems. The problem between principal and agent initiate costs. Some researchers divide agency cost by two: monitoring cost and bonding cost. Chen, Chen, Cheng and Shevlin (2010), corporate governance reduces monitoring cost by creating a higher level of control and transparency within the organization. Corporate governance is the way or manner in which organizations are controlled and directed. There are several corporate governance codes among which are the Securities and Exchange Commission governance codes and Bank codes of corporate governance. (Ilugbusi, Etal 2024)

Board Size

Board size is the total number of directors sitting on the board of any corporate organization. The determination of an ideal board size for an organization is very important because the number and quality of directors in a firm determines and influences the board functioning and hence firm performance. The board size is a fundamental component of the features of the board which permits coping with aggressive managerial manipulation. The Nigerian code of corporate governance practices recommended specific number of directors that must compose the board. This number presents the best size that promotes quick decision-making in the organization. Similarly, the literature argued that large boards are generally perceived as being less effective in the exchange of ideas, promoting coalition between board members as well as impinging aggressive tax measures. In the same vein, Gonzalez and Garcia-Meca believed that excessive board size can be an obstacle to speed and efficiency in decision-

making of organization owing to the factor that it may cause coordination and communication problems among members of the board. (Yusuf, & Adediran, 2024).

Corporate Board Independence

The independence of directors or the board has a number of internal and external directors. The independence of the directors provides effective control of managers as suggested by the agency theory. Undeniably, external members can ensure the competence and independence at the same time. Consequently, internal directors are frustrated by some dependence as their categorized rank relative to the management. The dependence of the directors prevent the ability of administrators against managerial decision-making. Recent empirical evidence in developed countries have shown that firms with a very independent board are less exposed to violations of accounting and tax matters. Minnick and Noga believed that the independent directors may be willing to adopt an effective tax management technique that is capable of improving business performance

Corporate Board Diversity This is the number of females represented on the board. The female board participation connotes where at least one female director exists on the board. The developing countries, such as Nigeria is beginning to recognize the fundamental role played by board diversity in an organization. Croson and Gneezy (2009) showed that the women are more risk averse than men, particularly in certain economical domains, and they are less involved than men in non-ethics behaviors. Kastlunger, et.al (2010) believed that women should expose higher levels of tax compliance. Nevertheless, the men should show important levels of tax evasion. The tendency of the men for the evasion of taxes is explained by several factors as the social differences. (Yusuf, 2026). Ogbeide, etal 2026)

Tax Aggressiveness

Tax aggressiveness is an act that has the objective to reduce taxable income through tax planning as well as using methods that are either classified or not classified as tax evasion. Although not all actions taken are against the rules, the more the methods used by the company should make the company assumed to be more tax-aggressive (Frank et al., 2009). By doing tax aggressiveness, the company can minimize the payment of income tax they owe. The smaller the amount of the income tax expense paid by the company, the higher level of tax aggressiveness. Conversely, the bigger the amount of corporate income tax payment, the lower the level of tax aggressiveness. Tax aggressiveness can be done in which anyone does not violate the law (tax planning) as well as breaking the rules (tax evasion), but they should be more tax aggressive to be agents' unlawful actions.

Tax aggressiveness is generally defined as the procedure of arranging one's affairs in order to defer, decrease or even eliminates the amount of taxes to be paid to the government (Pniowsky, 2010). Tax aggressiveness can be described as an act that has the objective to reduce taxable income through tax planning as well as using methods that are either classified or not classified as tax evasion. Tax aggressiveness refers the effort of corporate entities to reduce tax payments using aggressive tax planning activities and tax avoidance (Chen et al., 2010). Frank et al. (2009) noted that tax aggressiveness is the manipulation of corporate entities to engage themselves in order to lower tax

income due to a kind of tax planning that can be considered as tax management. This concept may have multiple conceptualizations, references and even different ways to measure, but most of them have the same meaning and the same purpose but differs in their repercussions on the companies' health. Bruce et al. (2007), states that tax aggressiveness can be defined as a simple trigger of tax management activities that corporate entities utilized for tax planning and have an arrival point for tax evasion. The belief is that tax aggressiveness reduces tax returns. Aggressive tax represents different handling activities to lower taxable income that can be legal or illegal. This study considered tax aggressiveness as a strategy employed by management of corporate organizations, a set of processes, practices, resources and choices whose objective is to maximize income after all corporate entities as well as their liabilities owed to the state and other stakeholders.

Figure 2.1: Conceptual Framework
Source: Author's Conceptualization, 2026

Theoretical Framework

Agency Theory

Agency theory was propounded by Jensen and Meckling in 1976. A contractual relationship that exists between an agent (manager) and the principal (shareholders) in which the shareholders bequeath the responsibilities to run the business to the manager is known as agency theory. Agency theory is about a contractual relationship between two or more persons. The development of corporate governance standards and principles is centered on agency theory (Fama & Jensen, 1983; Vafeas, 1999). The boards' structure, functions and composition are governed by the "principal and agent" with a view to reducing agency costs and ensure that managers maximized shareholder wealth (Conger, Finegold & Lawler, 2005).

Agency theory is a term that explains the relationship that exists when one person or group of persons (agents) act on behalf of the principal (shareholder). The essence of this theory is because of the likely conflict of separating ownership from the daily management of Organization (Oye, 2010). Jensen and Meckling (1976), affirm that agency relationship is a contractual arrangement between one or more person (principals) and another person (the agent) who is engaged and delegated with some decision-making authority by the principals to perform some service on their behalf. This theory addresses

particularly on one hand the principal-agent relationship between shareholders and directors and on the other hand the relationship between company agents and stakeholders (Hayes, Dassen, Schilder, & Wallage, 1999). The principals and agents in an agency relationship are also presumed to be reasonable economic individuals who have the capability of establishing objective expectations regarding the effect of agency problems in addition to the associated future value of their wealth (Barnea, Haugen, & Senbet, 1985). Jensen et al., (1976) posit that managers, who are agents of the principals (shareholders), are employed to work for maximizing the returns to the shareholders.

Similarly, different theories and definitions of aggressive tax have revealed that significantly, after tax returns could be uninterestedly influenced by tax minimization, while minimization of tax could be seen as tax aggressive benefit.

Empirical Review

Ogbeide and Obaretin (2018) examined corporate governance mechanisms and tax aggressiveness of listed firms in Nigeria. Inferential statistics consisting of General Method of Moment was used for the data analysis. The results obtained reveal that corporate governance mechanisms exert significant impact on tax aggressiveness in Nigeria. Specifically, ownership concentration and managerial ownership were positive and significantly impacts tax aggressiveness of listed non- financial firms in Nigeria whereas board size negatively and significantly impact tax aggressiveness over the reference period. Board gender diversity and board independence were significant and exert negative influence on tax aggressiveness of firms in Nigeria.

Amedu et al (2021) assessed the corporate governance (CG) structure and tax aggressiveness (TAG) of quoted manufacturing Companies in Nigeria. The longitudinal research design was used for the study. Panel regression was used to estimate the model for the study. The results reveal that; (i) The board size (BDS) has a positive effect on tax aggressiveness and significant at 10% , (ii) The effect of board independence (BDIND) is significant at 5% though with a negative coefficient (-0.0962) which suggest that increases in board independence reduces the level of tax aggressiveness, (iii) Board Gender diversity (BGD) has a positive effect on tax aggressiveness and also significant ($p=0.007$) at 5% which at suggest that an increase in the board female proportion increases corporate tax aggressiveness practice.

Lambe et al (2022) examined the effect of Corporate Governance Mechanisms on Tax Aggressiveness among Quoted Manufacturing Firms in Nigeria. The ex-post facto research design was used. The multiple regression equation was set up to investigate the hypothesized relationships between the dependent variable (tax aggressiveness) and independent variables (board size, board diversity, independent directors, proportion of non-executive directors to executive directors and return on asset as a control variable) in this study. Based on the analysis of data, it showed that when taken individually, board size and board diversity, both have a positive, but insignificant effect on tax aggressiveness, while return on asset (used as a control variable) has a positive and significant effect on tax aggressiveness. Based on the findings of the study concluded that there exists a significant

relationship between corporate governance mechanisms and tax aggressiveness of quoted manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

Uniamikogbo (2021) investigated the effect of corporate governance on tax aggressiveness in Nigeria. The secondary source of data collection method was used in generating data from the annual reports and accounts of the selected firms for the period 2013- 2017. Data generated were analyzed using descriptive statistics and Ordinary Least Square (OLS) regression. Findings from the study showed that a positive and significant relationship exists between gender diversity, board size and tax aggressiveness while a negative but significant relationship subsists between CEO duality and tax aggressiveness. Negative and insignificant relationship exists between ownership structure and tax aggressiveness in the Nigerian Oil & Gas marketing firms.

Akinpelu (2021) investigated the effect of corporate governance on tax aggressiveness among selected manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The expo-facto research design was employed in the study. The data obtained were analyzed using the Ordinary Least Square technique with its Best Linear Unbiased Estimate (BLUE) Property. Based on the analysis of data using the fixed effect regression, it was revealed that board size has no significant impact on tax aggressiveness while board diversity, independent director and proportion of non-executive directors to executive directors has a significant effect on tax aggressiveness on quoted manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Using the random effect regression model, a similar outcome was gotten.

Abubaka (2021) focused on Board of Directors' Structure and Corporate Tax Aggressiveness of Listed Industrial Goods Companies in Nigeria. Descriptive statistics, ordinary least square regression technique was used to estimate the model. Hausman's specification test was also conducted to choose between fixed and random effect, the test favoured random effect over fixed effect. The result reveals that firm size (FSZ) and leverage (LEV) are negatively related to tax rate while board size (BSZ), independent directors (IND) and return on equity (ROE) are positively related to tax rate. It was also found that an independent director (IND) was statistically significant at 1% level, while board size (BSZ) was negatively insignificant. The study concluded that board size (BSZ) has significant role to play in reducing tax aggressiveness of listed industrial goods in Nigeria.

Sule Ba'aba and Bashiru (2019) examined the impact of Corporate Governance Attributes on Tax planning of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria and Malaysia. The study adopted comparative and ex-post facto research design. The Data were analysed using a panel regression technique. Hausman specification test was conducted to choose between fixed and random effect estimation and the p-value is 0.9863 which insignificant. The results from random effect estimation model indicates a negative and significant relationship between CEOT, FSIZE and ETR and a positive relationship between BSIZE and ETR. Therefore, the study concluded that corporate governance mechanism plays a significant role in tax planning and Nigerian manufacturing companies pays high tax charges as compare to Malaysian food and beverages companies.

Omonitie and Obaretin (2021) examined the moderating effect of corporate governance on the relationship between corporate tax aggressiveness and firm financial performance. The study made use of the ex-post facto research design. Data for the study were analyzed using the random effect panel regression technique as indicated by the Hausman test. The study found that tax aggressiveness exhibited a negative relationship with firm performance but this was statistically insignificant when tested at the 5% level of significance. Corporate governance was found to exhibit a positive relationship with firm performance and this was statistically significant when tested at a 5% level of significance. Corporate governance was found not to have a significant moderating effect on the relationship between tax aggressiveness and firm performance when tested at a 5% level of significance.

Onatuyeh & Ukolobi (2021) explored the Tax Aggressiveness, Corporate Governance and Audit Fees: A Study of Listed Firms in Nigeria. 2018). the panel regression technique, with preference for the random effect model based on the outcome of the Hausman test, was employed to estimate the balanced panel data. The results of the study showed that cash tax rate, audit committee diligence and board independence all exert positive and significant effect on audit fees. Surprisingly, the study revealed a positive but statistically insignificant link between board gender diversity and audit fees.

Yinka and Saliu (2022) focused on the effect of good corporate governance attributes on the tax compliance behavior of listed firms in Nigeria from 2012-2016. Data for corporate governance attributes were extracted from the annual reports of the sample firms and those of the tax compliance indices were extracted from their files with the tax office. Based on the result of the Hausman test, the fixed-effect model was used as a basis for the discussion of findings. Findings suggest that managerial ownership and non-executive director have significant positive relationship with tax compliance. Board size has a negative relationship while the effects of gender diversity, auditor profile, ownership concentration, and institutional ownership are not significant.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study made use of an ex-post-facto research design. The choice of this research design is because our data are numerical and we want to ascertain the relationship between the variables of the study.

Model Specification in the Model

The model adopted specified of the functional form:

$$TA = \beta + \beta_1 BS_1 + \beta_2 BI_2 + \beta_3 BD_3 + \mu$$

Where;

TAA = Tax Aggressive Avoidance

BS = Board Size

BI = Board Independence

BD = Board Diversity

β = Constant term (intercept)

μ = Error Term

β_1 - β_3 are parameters of estimation. The subscripts i and t refer to individual firms and time period (2013-2022) respectively. The apriori expectations of the study are of the form: β_1 - $\beta_5 > 0$. This apriori signs imply that the explanatory variables in the models are expected to be positive impact on tax aggressiveness in line with the theoretical framework of the study as well as in affirmation of extant literature

Description of Variables

The variables in this research work are divided into two; we have the dependent and independent variables.

Variable Acronym	Variable Name	Variable Type	Measurement
TAA	Tax Aggressive avoidance	Dependent	Effective Tax Rate: Tax aggressiveness is measured by Tax Rate (TRT). (Total Tax Expenses/Pre- Tax Income] X 100)
BS	Board Size	Independent	Board size (measured as natural log of total number of directors)
BI	Board Independence	Independent	Percentage of independent directors on the board for company i in time t
BD	Board Diversity	Independent	Board diversity is measured in terms of percentages of women in the board for company i in time t ,

Source: Author's Compilation, 2024.

4.0 DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Presentation of data

Table 4.1: Panel Data for the Sampled Insurance Firms in Nigeria

INSURANCECOMPANY	YEAR	TAA	BS	BI	BD
AIICO INSURANCE	2016	78.740	9	44.44	22.2
AIICO INSURANCE	2017	344.76	9	44.4	33.3
AIICO INSURANCE	2018	265.00	9	44.4	33.3
AIICO INSURANCE	2019	372.33	9	28.57	33.3
AIICO INSURANCE	2020	148.19	9	28.57	33.3
AIICO INSURANCE	2021	160.58	9	28.57	33.3
AIICO INSURANCE	2022	292.70	7	28.57	33.3
AIICO INSURANCE	2023	281.34	7	28.57	33.3
AIICO INSURANCE	2024	338.22	7	28.57	33.3
AIICO INSURANCE	2025	389.10	7	28.57	33.3

Michigan International Journal of Corporate Finance and Accounting

Volume 14 Issue 2, April-June 2026

ISSN: 2836-4037

Impact Factor: 9.61

Journal Homepage: <https://americaserial.com/Journals/index.php/MIJCFA>

Email: contact@americaserial.com

Official Journal of America Serial Publication

AXA MANSARD INS	2016	2013.1	7	28.57	33.3
AXA MANSARD INS	2017	3029.1	7	28.57	33.3
AXA MANSARD INS	2018	2944.1	7	28.57	33.3
AXA MANSARD INS	2019	2264.31	8	62.5	12.5
AXA MANSARD INS	2020	43.267	8	62.5	12.5
AXA MANSARD INS	2021	46.76	8	62.5	12.5
AXA MANSARD INS	2022	21.57	8	62.5	12.5
AXA MANSARD INS	2023	37.80	7	42.86	14.28
AXA MANSARD INS	2024	43.93	9	55.55	11.11
AXA MANSARD INS	2025	39.1	9	55.55	11.11
NEM INSURANCE	2016	370	9	55.55	11.11
NEM INSURANCE	2017	30.02	9	55.55	11.11
NEM INSURANCE	2018	27.29	9	55.55	11.11
NEM INSURANCE	2019	20.31	9	55.55	11.11
NEM INSURANCE	2020	7.545	10	50.0	10.00
NEM INSURANCE	2021	58.10	10	50.0	10.00
NEM INSURANCE	2022	20.48	10	50.0	10.00
NEM INSURANCE	2023	38.34	10	50.0	10.00
NEM INSURANCE	2024	43.40	10	50.0	20.00
NEM INSURANCE	2025	34.95	10	50.0	20.00
HAIRS INSURANCS	2016	5.321	9	88.88	0
HAIRS INSURANCS	2017	32.74	9	88.88	0
HAIRS INSURANCS	2018	18.07	9	77.77	0
HAIRS INSURANCS	2019	4.88	9	77.77	0
HAIRS INSURANCS	2020	7.545	10	80.0	0
HAIRS INSURANCS	2021	58.10	10	80.0	0
HAIRS INSURANCS	2022	20.48	10	80.0	0
HAIRS INSURANCS	2023	38.34	10	80.0	0
HAIRS INSURANCS	2024	43.40	10	80.0	0
HAIRS INSURANCS	2025	34.95	10	80.0	0
LEADWAY INSURANCE	2016	282.501	11	72.72	0
LEADWAY INSURANCE	2017	15.32	11	72.72	0
LEADWAY INSURANCE	2018	6.31	11	72.72	9.09

LEADWAY INSURANCE	2019	31.74	11	72.72	9.09
LEADWAY INSURANCE	2020	1.62	12	58.33	16.66
LEADWAY INSURANCE	2021	11.08	12	58.33	16.66
LEADWAY INSURANCE	2022	27.69	11	63.63	27.27
LEADWAY INSURANCE	2023	28.55	11	63.63	27.27
LEADWAY INSURANCE	2024	4.70	12	58.33	16.66
LEADWAY INSURANCE	2025	4.70	12	58.33	16.66

Source: Author's compilation from Annual Report and Account of the Selected Firms

Table 4.1 Descriptive Statistics for the Selected Pharmaceutical Firms

	TAA	BS	BI	BD
Mean	289.6494	9.320000	56.19720	15.44200
Median	38.34000	9.000000	55.55000	12.50000
Maximum	3029.100	12.00000	88.88000	33.30000
Minimum	1.620000	7.000000	28.57000	0.000000
Std. Dev.	698.2456	1.448997	18.24223	12.29655
Skewness	3.115315	-0.002732	-0.097998	0.290723
Kurtosis	11.40330	2.365686	2.045161	1.779833
Jarque-Bera Probability	227.9922 0.000000	5.838300 0.007605	5.979440 0.031681	3.806017 0.009119
Sum	14482.47	466.0000	2809.860	772.1000
Sum Sq. Dev.	23889797	102.8800	16306.17	7409.047
Observations	50	50	50	50

Source: Author's Computation from EViews 10.0 Statistical Software

Table 4.1 above reveals the variable description of the 50 observations of the panel data for sampled Insurance firm in Nigeria. From the table, the industry's minimums include Tax management (1.620000), Board Size (7.000000), Board Independence (28.57000), and Board Diversity (0.000000). However, the industry's maximum includes Tax management (3029.100), Board Size (12.00000), Board Independence (88.88000), Board Diversity (33.30000). The industry means for

the variables studied are: Tax management (289.6494), Board Size (9.320000), Board Independence (56.19720), Board Diversity (15.44200).

The normality of the distribution of the data series is shown by the coefficients of Skewness, Kurtosis, and Jarque-Bera Probability.

Test of Hypotheses Formulated

The result of the regression analysis is presented in is presented as table 4.3 and is interpreted below.

Dependent Variable: TAA

Method: Panel Least Squares

Date: 09/04/26 Time: 14:47

Sample: 2016 2026

Periods included: 10

Cross-sections included: 5

Total panel (balanced) observations: 50

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
BS	-192.6616	70.90225	-2.717285	0.0092
BI	2.091038	11.34637	0.184291	0.8546
BD	16.39644	15.77177	1.039607	0.3040
C	1714.552	909.1021	1.885983	0.0656
R-squared	0.891981	Mean dependent var		289.6494
Adjusted R-squared	0.845806	S.D. dependent var		698.2456
S.E. of regression	606.3867	Akaike info criterion		15.72953
Sum squared resid	16914420	Schwarz criterion		15.88249
Log likelihood	-389.2383	Hannan-Quinn criter.		15.78778
F-statistic	6.323349	Durbin-Watson stat		2.447467
Prob(F-statistic)	0.001108			

Eviews 10.0 Statistical Software

Regression coefficient

$$TA_{it} = 1714.552 - 192.6616 + 2.091038 + 16.39644$$

Interpretation of Regression Coefficient

Table 4.3 shows the coefficient of regression result for the insurance firms. The coefficient of Tax Aggressiveness management is negative for Board Size while it is positive for Board Size. It indicates that a unit/one naira change in the explanatory variables of Corporate Governance as explained by Board Size, (BS) will yield a decrease of -192.6616. On the other hand, a unit/one naira change in the

explanatory variables of as explained by Board Independence (BI) and Board Diversity will yield an increase of 2.091038 and 16.39644 in TA of insurance firms.

In table 4.3, R-squared and its adjusted R-squared values were significant respectively. This is an indication that all the independent variables jointly explain about 29% of the systematic variations in Tax Aggressiveness (TA) of pharmaceutical firms over the ten years (2013-2022) while 79% of the systematic variations are captured by the error term. The F-statistics of 6.323349 and its P-value of (0.001108) portray the fact that the regression model is well specified.

Decision Rule:

1. Reject H_0 if the P-Value $\text{cal} < 0.05$ at 5% level of significance.
2. Otherwise, accept the null hypothesis (H_0).

Test of Hypothesis

Hypothesis One: Corporate Board Size has no significant effect on tax aggressiveness of pharmaceutical firms in Nigeria. **Decision:** From the panel regression analysis in Table 4.3, based on the t-value of -2.717285 and P-value of 0.0092, in table 4.3 was found that Corporate Board Size has a negative influence on the insurance firms Tax Aggressiveness (TA) and this influence is statistically significant at 5% level of significance as the P-value is within 5% significance level. This result, therefore suggests that we should accept our alternate hypothesis one (H_1) which states Corporate Board Size has a significant effect on tax aggressiveness of insurance firms in Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two: Corporate Board Independence does not significantly affect tax aggressiveness of insurance firms in Nigeria. **Decision:** From the panel regression analysis in Table 4.3, based on the t-value of 0.184291 and P-value of 0.8546, in table 4.3, it was found that Corporate Board Independence have a positive influence on the insurance firms Tax Aggressiveness (TA) and this influence is statistically non-significant at 5% level of significance as the P-value is not within 5% significance level. This result, therefore suggests that we should accept our null hypothesis two (H_{02}) which states Corporate Board Independence does not significantly affect tax aggressiveness of pharmaceutical firms in Nigeria.

Hypothesis Three: Corporate Board Diversity has no significant effect on tax aggressiveness of pharmaceutical firms in Nigeria. **Decision:** From the panel regression analysis in Table 4.3, based on the t-value of 1.039607 and P-value of 0.3040, in table 4.3, it was found that Corporate Board Diversity has a positive influence on the insurance firms Tax Aggressiveness (TA) and this influence is statistically non-significant at 5% level of significance as the P-value is not within 5% significance level. This result, therefore suggests that we should accept our null hypothesis three (H_3) which states Corporate Board Diversity has no significant effect on tax aggressiveness of insurance firms in Nigeria.

5.0 SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary of Findings

In line with the four hypotheses tested and the result of the analysis, the following are the findings of the study: Corporate Board Size had a significant effect on tax aggressiveness of insurance firms in Nigeria. The panel regression analysis in Table 4.3, the t-value = -2.717285 and P-value = 0.0092. This

suggests that increase in board independence reduces the level of tax aggressiveness management Corporate Board Independence does not significantly affect tax aggressiveness managements of insurance firms in Nigeria. This is based on where the t-value 0.184291 and P-value = 0.8546. This supports the proposition that increases in the proportion of Non-Executive Directors decrease tax compliance and decrease aggressive tax planning Corporate Board Diversity has no significant effect on tax aggressiveness of insurance firms in Nigeria. This implies that an increasing proportion of Board Diversity associated with decrease in effective tax rate.

Conclusion

In view of the findings, the study concluded that corporate governance has not influenced tax aggressiveness managements among the insurance firms in Nigeria. This is because corporate tax aggressiveness is considered as one of the most severe compliance issue threatening Nigeria and most nations of the world. This menace may manifest in the form of reducing tax liabilities, engaging in tax avoidance which remains prevalent among corporate firms given the magnitude of the income taxes which take away a more significant proportion of firm's pre-tax earnings and subsequently reduce their distributable profit.

Recommendations

Because of the finding and conclusion, the following recommendations were made:

In light of the findings of this study, corporate entities should maintain a moderate board size, the recommendation arises due to the need to facilitate quality and timely decision-making, board efficacy, and compliance with tax law provisions and authority. The study recommends that the presence of tax aggressiveness in an organization will affect financial performance negatively. It is therefore recommended that management should examine their tax aggressive activities to ensure that it does not affect the performance of the firm negatively. That quoted insurance firms in Nigeria should give value to diversity in the board composition within the firm as diversity in the board decreases tax aggressiveness

REFERENCE

- Al Arussi, et al (2009).Determinants, of financial and environmental disclosures through the internet by Malaysian companies *Asian review of accounting* 17(1), 59-76.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/13217340910956513>
- Aliani, K., M'hamid, I., & Zarai, M. (2011) Effect of sex and gender diversity in board of directors on tax *optimization* of the *Tunisian* companies.
- Alstadsacter, A., & Jacob, M. (2013) who participant in tax avoidance? Working paper. University of Osloand: WHU-Otto
- Annuar,H.A., Salihu, I. A., & Obid, S. N. S. (2014). Corporate ownership, governance and tax avoidance: An interactive effects. *Procedia. Social and Behavioural Sciences*, 164 (2014), 150 -160.

- Bayar, O., Huseynov, F., & Sardarli, S. (2018). Corporate Governance, tax Avoidance, and Financial Constraints. *Financial management*, 47(3), 651- 677
- Bhagat, S., & Bolton, B. (2008). Corporate governance and firm performance. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 14 (3), 257-273.
- Bliss, M. A. (2011). Does CEO duality constrain board independence? Some evidence from audit pricing. *Accounting & Finance*, 51(2), 361-380.
- Blouin, J. (2014). Defining and measuring tax planning aggressiveness. *National Tax Journal*, 67(4), 875-900.
- Booth, J., Cornett, M., & Tehranian, H. (2002). Boards of directors, ownership, and regulation. *Journal of banking & Finance*, 26(10), 1973-1996.
- Boussaidi, A., & Hamed, M. S. (2015). The impact of governance mechanisms on tax aggressiveness: Empirical evidence from Tunisian context. *Journal of Asian business Strategy*, 5(1), 1-12.
- Braithwaite, J. (2005). *Markets in Vice, Markets in Virtue*. New South Wales, Sydney: Federation Press.
- Bushman, R.M., & Smith, A. J. (2001). Financial accounting information and corporate governance. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 32(1-3), 237-333.
- Chapra, M. U., & Ahmed, H. (2002). Corporate governance in Islamic financial institutions. Islamic Research and Training Institute, 'Islamic development Bank, Saudi Arabia.
- Chen, S., Chen, X., Cheng, Q., & Shevlin, T. (2010). Are family firms more tax aggressive than non-family firms? *Journal of Financial Economics*, 95(1), 41-61.
- Cremers, K. J., & Nair, V. B. (2005). Governance mechanisms and equity prices. *The Journal*, 60(6), 2859-2894.
- Dalwai, T. A. R., Basiruddin, R., & Abdul Rasid, S. Z. (2015). A critical review of relationship between corporate governance and firm performance: GCC banking sector perspective. *Corporate Governance*, 15(1), 18-30.
- Denis, D. K., & McConnell, J. J. (2003). International corporate governance. *Journal of Financial and Quantitative Analysis*, 38(1), 1 -36.
- Desai, M. A., & Dharmapala, D. (2009). Tax and corporate governance: An economic approach MPI Studies on Intellectual Property, Competition and Tax Law, 3, 13-30.

Dyrenge, S. D., Hanlon, M., & Maydew, E. L. (2010). The effects of executives on corporate tax avoidance. *The Accounting Review*, 85(4), 1163-1189.

Edame, G. E., & Okoi, W. W. (2014). The impact of taxation on investment and economic development in Nigeria. *Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*, 3(4), 209 -218. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.5901/ajis.2014.v3n4p209>

Edwin, O. A. & Victor, O. (2019). Corporate board characteristics and tax aggressiveness: a study of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. *Management* 8(4), Print ISSN No 2277-8160.

Effiong, S. A., Akpan, E. I., & Oti, P.A. (2012). Corporate Governance, Wealthy Creation and Social Responsibility Accounting. *Management Science and engineering*, 6(4), 110-114. Available from: <http://www.cscanda.net/inde.php/mse/article/view/j.mse.1913035X20120604.559> DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.3968/j.mse.1913035X20120604.559>.

Fadhilah, R. (2014). Pengaruh (Good Corporate Governance) Terhadap (Tax avoidance) (Bachelor Thesis). Universitas Negeri Padang

Firth, M., Fung, P., & Rui, O. (2007). Ownership, two-tier board structure, and the informativeness of earnings. Evidence from China. *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*, 26(4), 463 – 496.

Franca, et al (2015). Tributaco Implicata e Clintelas, Arbitragem, Restricoes e Friccoes. *Revista de Administracao e Contabilidade da FAT*, 7(1), 5-18.

Gebba, T. R. (2015). Corporate governance mechanisms adopted by UAE national commercial banks. *Journal of Applied Finance and Banking*, 5(5), 23-61

Gravelle, J. G. (2013). Tax havens, international tax avoidance and evasion. Congressional Research Service.

Hanlon, M, & Slemrod. J (2009). What does tax aggressiveness signal? Evidence from stock price reaction to news above tax shelter involvement. *Journal of public economics*, 93(1-2), 126-141.

Hanlon, M. & Heitzman, S. (2010). A reviewer of tax research. *Journal of accounting and economics* 50(2). 127-178.

Ideh, A. O., & Okolo, M. N. (2025). Board structure on tax aggressiveness: A focus on non-financial listed firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 9(8), 4592–4604. <https://dx.doi.org/10.47772/IJRISS.2025.908000367>

- Ilugbusi, B. S., Olutoye, A. E., Surulere, O. J., & Ige, F. F. (2024). The impact of corporate governance mechanisms on organisational efficiency of listed financial firms in Nigeria. *African Journal of Stability and Development*, 16(2), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.53982/ajsd.2024.1602.16-j>
- Jalali, M, Jalali, F. Moridi, Garshasbi A, & Foroodi, A. (2013) the impact of board of directors structure on tax avoidance in the companies listed in Tehran stock exchange. *International research journal of applied and basic science*, 4(9). 2526-2531.
- John-Akamelu, C. R., Igwedibia, A., & Ekeh, G. (2024). Effect of corporate tax aggressiveness strategies on firm growth in Nigeria. *Interdisciplinary Journal of African and Asian Studies*, 8(2), 55–72.
- Karaibrahimoglu, Y.Z. (2013). Is corporate governance a determinant of auditor choice? Evidence from Turkey. *Ege academic review*, 13(2), 273-284.
- Kurawa, J, M. & Saidu, H. (2018) corporate tax and financial performance of list Nigerian consumer goods. *Journal of accounting and financial management* 4(4) ISSN2504-www.iiardpub.org. IIARD-internation . Institute of academic research and development.
- Lanis, R. & Richard, G. (2011). The effect of board director's composition on corporate tax aggressiveness. *Journal of accounting and public policy*, 30(1) 50-70.
- Lim, Y. (2011). Tax avoidance, cost of debt and shareholder activism: evidence from Korea. *Journal of banking & finance*, 35(2), 456-470.
- Lisowsky, P. (2009). Interfering U.S tax liability from financial statement information. *The journal of the American association*, 31(1), 29-63.
- Maier, S. (2005). How global is good corporate governance. London ethical investment research services.
- Martinez, A.L (2017). Tax aggressiveness: a literature survey. *Revista de Educacao e pesquisa em contabilidade (journal of Education and research in accounting)*, 11(special edition, 6), 104-121. Available online at: www.repec.org.br. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.17524/repec.v11i0.1724>.
- Mgbame, C.O. Chijoke-Mgbame, M.A, Yekini, S. & Kemi, Y.C. (2017). Corporate social responsibility performance and tax aggressiveness. *Journal of accounting and taxation*, 9(8), 101-108.
- Mills, L.F, Nutter, S.E, & Schwab, C.M. (2013). The effect of political sensitivity and bargaining power on taxes: evidence from federal contractors. *The accounting review*, 88 (3), 977-1005.

Minick, K. & Noga, T (2010). Do corporate governance characteristics influence tax management? *Journal of corporate finance*, 16 (5), 703-718.

Ogbeide, I. O., Anyaduba, J. O., & Akogo, O. U. (2022). Firm attributes and corporate tax aggressiveness in Nigeria. *American Journal of Finance*, 7(2), 64–87. <https://doi.org/10.47672/ajf.1100>

Okpala, N., & Omaliko, E. (2022). Corporate governance mechanisms and tax sheltering: Evidence from quoted firms in Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting*, 22(19), 149–158. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajeba/2022/v22i1930666>

Organization for economic Co-operate and development [OECD], (2004). Principles of corporate governance. OECD publication service. Organization for Economic Co-operation and development [OECD], (1999). OECD Principles of Corporate Governance. Ad Hoc Task Force on Corporate Governance, OECD, Paris.

Osuegbu, E. O. (2007). Good tax planning as legal options to the illegality of tax evasion. A paper delivered at the tax awareness forum for public and organized private sector organized by the Federal Inland Revenue Service.

Pilos, N. V. D. (2017). Tax Avoidance and Corporate Governance- Does the board of directors influence tax avoidance? (Unpublished Master's Thesis). Erasmus School Of Economics, Erasmus University.

Poudel, R. I. (2015). Relationship between Corporate Governance and Corporate Governance and Corporate Social Responsibility: Evidence from Nepalese Commercial Banks. *Journal of Napalese Business Studies*, 9(1), 137-144.

Prastiwi, D. (2017). Does corporate governance moderate the effect of earnings management on tax aggressiveness? *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research (ASSEHR)*, 108, 8-13.

Proshare, (2019). The FRCN Nigerian Code of Corporate Governance 2018. Available online at: Solomon, J., & Solomon, A. (2004). *Corporate Governance and Accountability*. Chichester: John Wiley & Sons.

Salawu, R. O., Ogundipe, L. O., & Yeye, O. (2017). Granger causality between corporate tax planning and firm value of non-financial quoted companies in Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*. ISSN 219 (Print), 2219-6021 (Online) DOI: 10.30845/ijbss.

- Shaba, Y., & Idris, S. (2024). Corporate governance in Nigeria: Evolution, regulatory frameworks and challenges. *Asian Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting*, 24(10), 356–367. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajeba/2024/v24i101533>
- Takumah, W. (2014). Tax revenue and economic growth in Ghana: A conitegration approach. MPRA Paper No. 58532. Available online at: https://mpra.ub.uni-muenchen.de/58532/1/MPRA_paper_58532.pdf.
- Tandean, V. A., & Winnie, W. (2016). The effect of good corporate governance on tax avoidance: An empirical study on manufacturing companies listed in IDX period 2010-2013. *Asian Journal of Accounting Research*, 1(1), 28-38.
- Uchendu, O., Ironkwe, U.I. & Nwaiwu, J.N. (2016). Corporate governance mechanism and tax planning in Nigeria. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research/ Social & Management Sciences*, 2(9), ISSN: 2488- 9849.
- Yusoff, W.F.W., & Alhaji, I.A. (2012). Insight of corporate governance theories. *Journal of Business and Management*, 1(1), 52-63.
- Yusuf, B. R., & Adediran, S. A. (2024). Determinants of corporate tax aggressiveness in Nigerian deposit money banks. *Malete Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 4(2), 14–29.
- Yusuf, N. R. (2026). External determinants of tax aggressiveness of listed non-financial companies in Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Accounting Perspectives*, 18(2), 1–32. <https://doi.org/10.22452/AJAP.vol18no2.1>
- Zalata, A., & Roberts, C. (2016). Internal corporate governance and classification shifting practice: An analysis of UK corporate behaviour, *Journal of Accounting, Auditing & Finance*, 31 (1), 51-78.
- Zemzem, A., & Khaoula, F. (2013). The effects of board of directors' characteristics on tax aggressiveness. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 4(4), 140-147.